

ISSUES OF FORMATION OF STATE CADASTRE DATA OF HIGHWAYS USING GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

U.A.Raximov

F.M.Tojidinova

Sh.Sh.Po'latov

“Samarkand State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering named after Mirzo Ulugbekh”, Lolazor str., 70\140147 Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

Correspondence:ulugbekraximovulugbek@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7726813>

Abstract: This article provides recommendations on attributive data of the thematic layers of state cadastre objects of highways, indicators of their legal, economic and construction status, and issues of providing state authorities, interested legal entities and individuals with reliable cadastral information on highway objects.

Keywords: geographic, automobile, attributive data, cadastre, geospatial information.

Taking into account the geographical location of our republic, the development of a modern highway network is a first-class task in increasing the competitiveness of our country's economy, developing the republic's transport potential, and expanding export opportunities.

Currently, the length of existing highways in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 184,000 km, which, in turn, requires the formation of information on the state cadastre of highways.

The State Committee of Highways of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the authorized body for maintaining the state cadastre of highways.

Maintaining the state cadastre of highways includes state registration of ownership rights and other rights to highway objects, accounting for quantitative and qualitative descriptions, evaluation in terms of quality and value, categorization, storage and updating of cadastral information, provision of relevant information for inclusion in the unified system of state cadastres, users includes provision of cadastral information. The concept of attribute data will help us in this.

The attributive database contains all information about highway objects, including their purpose of use, total length and width, occupied land plots, service buildings and special structures, owners, users, geographical location, legal status, quantity descriptions and evaluation, as well as they will consist of current changes in condition, materials used, year of construction and date of acceptance for use, and other relevant indicators.

"Overview of highways" "Highways", "Artificial constructions", "Regulation and equipment objects", "Road intersections and junctions", "Protective structures" and " Creating attributive data of the thematic layers of "buildings-structures", creating reports on the state of their legal, economic management and construction status indicators, and creating cadastral information is considered one of the main indicators in creating and maintaining the state cadastre of highways.

The specialized geographic information system is designed to solve the issues of the unified system of State cadastres based on the computer base of these data, taking into account the attributive data of the thematic layers of the state cadastre of highways by "Categories of the street-road network" and the information representing their legal, economic management and construction status (Unified system of state cadastres, GIS), that is, we form their attribute data in order to ensure the integration of thematic cadastral information into a single geospatial information base (Fig. 1).

In this case, the location of highways, their property rights or other material rights belonging to legal entities and individuals, the basis and terms of the emergence of these rights, their suspension periods, the conditions for limiting property rights and other material rights, state registration, the protection installed on these objects information about the territory is information about the legal status of highways. The value of highways and their technical condition and state of repair, their types according to the purpose of their use, departmental affiliation to higher authorities and other information constitute the economic status of highways.

Figure 1. Content of attributive data of the thematic layers of highway objects according to the state cadastre.

Compliance of highways with land development schemes, master plans of cities, settlement projects, as well as requirements of urban planning norms and rules, parameters of highways (total length, width-general and carriageway, number of traffic lanes) and types of materials of the carriageway, The construction status of highways is the land plot, date of construction, availability of engineering and technical facilities, highway service buildings and other technical information. If it is prepared on the basis of attributive data of the thematic layers of state cadastre objects of highways and their legal, economic management and construction status indicators (Fig.1), it will help to provide state authorities and management bodies, interested legal entities and individuals with reliable cadastral information about highway objects. benefits.

References:

1. Рахимов, У. А. (2022, September). МАДАНИЙ МЕРОС ОБЪЕКТЛАРИНИ ЖОЙЛАШГАН ЎРНИНИ GNSS ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИДАН Фойдаланиб Аниқлаш. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 168-173).
2. Abdullayevich, R. U. B. (2022, June). MODDIY MADANIY MEROS OBYEKTЛАRI DAVLAT KADASTRI BO'YICHA TEMATIK QATLAMLARINING ATRIBUTIV MA'LUMOTLARINI YARATISH. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 8-12).
3. Abdullayevich, R. U. B. (2022, June). CREATION OF ATTRIBUTIVE DATA OF THEMATIC STRUCTURES OF THE STATE CADASTRE OF MATERIAL CULTURAL HERITAGE OBJECTS. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 1-5).
4. Раимов, У. А., & Тухтаев, Ш. Х. (2021, October). Геодезический Мониторинг Деформаций Ансамбля Регистан. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 96-100).
5. Khujayorovich, E.I., & Abdullayevich, U.R. (2020). Formation of Protection Zones of Tangible and Cultural Heritage Objects on Republican and Local Significance.
6. Ф.Чоршанбаев, У.Рахимов. “Тарихий ёдгорликлар ҳақида маълумотлар банкини яратиш ва юритиш концепцияси”. Геодезия, картография ва кадастр соҳаларини ривожлантиришнинг долзарб муаммолари” республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. 2014 йил, 121-122 бетлар. СамДАҚИ.
7. У.А.Рахимов, Б.Абриев. “ArcGIS 9.3 дастуридан фойдаланиб, тарихий маданий объектлар тўғрисида сайёҳлик ва оммабоп электрон хариталарини яратиш”. Таълим, фан ва ишлаб чиқариш интеграциясида инновацион технологияларни қўллаш-мамлакат тараққиётининг муҳим омили” мавзусидаги XV республика илмий-техник конференцияси материаллари. 2018 йил, 1-китоб, 20-23 бетлар. СамДАҚИ.
8. Erkin Isakov Khujayorovich and Ulugbek Rakhimov Abdullayevich. “Formation of Protection Zones of Tangible and Cultural Heritage Objects on Republican and Local Significance”. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) ISSN: 2509-0119. Vol. 23 No. 2 November 2020, pp. 385-392. 385-392 бетлар.
9. Рахимов У.А. “Моддий маданий мерос объектларининг маълумотлар Банкини яратиш ва юритишда замонавий электрон геодезик Дастурларнинг аҳамияти”. Memorchilik va qurilish Muammolari (ilmiy-texnik jurnal) МАХСУС СОН Erasmus+ дастурининг “DSinGIS-Геоинформатика

THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

соҳасида докторантура” лойиҳаси доирасида “Геоахборот тизими (ГАТ) технологияси соҳасини ривожлантиришнинг долзарб муаммолари ва ечимлари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий - амалий конференция танланган илмий ишлар тўплами. 2019 йил,67-70 бетлар. СамДАҚИ.

